

PCP WISE

D2.2 Dissemination Strategy

Impact Maximisation

GAC

Funded by
the European Union

Document title	D2.2 Dissemination Strategy
Project acronym	PCP WISE
Project title	The customisation/pre-operationalisation of water management innovations from space for European climate resilience
Thematic priority	HORIZON-CL6-2024-GOVERNANCE-01
Type of action	Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP)
Deliverable number and title	D2.2 Dissemination Strategy
Task	Task 2.1 & Task 2.2
Work package	WP2 – Impact Maximisation
Due date	March 2025 (M3) but it was agreed with the PA to postpone the deliverable due date to 2 June 2025 (M6)
Submission date	2 June 2025
Start date of the project	01/01/2025
End date of the project	31/12/2027
Deliverable responsible partner	GAC
Version	1.0
Status	Final
Author(s) name(s)	Mélissa Campagno (GAC), Sofiane Bari (GAC)
Contributing partners	Mélissa Campagno, Sofiane Bari, Marc Pattinson (GAC)
Reviewer(s)	Lúa Legazpi Gil, Rocío Beneyto Calvo, Pablo J. Martínez, Alejandro Fernández de Mera Rico (Barrabés) Ana Lucia Jaramillo, Ana Isabel Peiró, Maria Kampa (Corvers)
Document type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> O – Other
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU – Public <input type="checkbox"/> SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Disclaimer

This document is provided with no warranties whatsoever, including any warranty of merchantability, non-infringement, fitness for any particular purpose, or any other warranty with respect to any information, result, proposal, specification, or sample contained or referred to herein. Any liability, including liability for infringement of any proprietary rights, regarding the use of this document or any information contained herein is disclaimed. No license, express or implied, by estoppel or otherwise, to any intellectual property rights is granted by or in connection with this document. This document is subject to change without notice. PCP WISE has been financed with support from the European Commission. This document reflects only the view of the author(s) and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained herein.

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	25/05/2025	Mélissa Campagno, Sofiane Bari (GAC)	First Draft
0.2	26/05/2025	Marc Pattinson (GAC)	First Draft review
0.3	27/05/2025	Lúa Legazpi Gil, Rocío Beneyto Calvo, Pablo J. Martínez, Alejandro Fernández de Mera Rico (Barrabés), Ana Lucia Jaramillo, Ana Isabel Peiró, Maria Kampa (Corvers)	Quality review
1.0	02/06/2025	Mélissa Campagno (GAC)	Final draft

Document abstract

This deliverable outlines the PCP WISE dissemination strategy to maximise visibility, engagement, and uptake of project results. It defines key messages, stakeholder segmentation, channels, tools, and responsibilities across the consortium. Aligned with the PCP process, the plan supports targeted outreach to suppliers, public buyers, and policy actors. It also introduces a preliminary exploitation and IPR strategy based on Horizon Europe PCP rules, ensuring appropriate access and ownership of results. The plan will evolve throughout the project and inform the Exploitation Plan at Month 17, supporting the long-term impact of PCP WISE innovations.

Keywords

Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP), Dissemination Strategy, Exploitation of Results, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), Earth Observation (EO), Innovation Procurement, Climate Resilience, Water innovations, Market uptake.

Table of Contents

List of figures.....	6
List of tables.....	6
List of abbreviations.....	7
Introduction.....	8
1. Dissemination of project results	9
1.1. PCP WISE Dissemination Strategy	9
1.1.1. Objectives.....	9
1.1.2. Target audiences	10
1.1.3. Key messages to be disseminated.....	11
1.1.4. Dissemination tools and channels.....	14
1.1.5. Timeline of dissemination activities.....	15
1.2. Partner-specific roles in dissemination.....	16
1.3. Dissemination KPI.....	17
2. Exploitation of Results.....	18
2.1. PCP WISE exploitation strategy.....	18
2.1.1. Commercial and policy-oriented exploitation strategy	18
2.1.2. Scientific exploitation and knowledge transfer	18
2.1.3. Partners' role and responsibilities.....	19
2.1.4. Planning of exploitation activities.....	19
2.2. IPR Strategy	19
2.2.1. Purpose and principles.....	19
2.2.2. IPR allocation and legal framework	20
2.2.3. IPR management across PCP phases.....	20
2.2.4. Risk mitigation measures	21
2.2.5. Post-project use and licensing	21
2.2.6. Oversight and responsibilities.....	21
3. Conclusion & Next Steps	21

List of figures

FIGURE 1: PCP WISE STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY. SOURCE: GRANT AGREEMENT 10

List of tables

TABLE 1: STAKEHOLDER TIERS' DEFINITION 10

TABLE 2: EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDER GLOSSARY 11

TABLE 3: PCP WISE KEY MESSAGES AND RESULTS TO BE DISSEMINATED 13

TABLE 4. PCP WISE DISSEMINATION CHANNELS..... 15

TABLE 5: TIMELINE OF PCP WISE DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS' PREPARATION 16

TABLE 6: PCP WISE KPI TABLE 17

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
EG	Enrich Global
EO	Earth Observation
FRAND	Fair, Reasonable, and Non-Discriminatory
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OMC	Open Market Consultation
PBG	Public Buyers Group
PCP	Pre-Commercial Procurement
WP	Work Package

Introduction

The PCP WISE project addresses the urgent need to improve climate resilience through better water management by leveraging EO technologies. As a PCP initiative, it drives innovation from the demand side, empowering public authorities to co-develop tailored solutions with EO providers. Dissemination is an essential function in this process. It aims to make project results available to those who can use them—end-users, researchers, policymakers, industry, and civil society. In PCP WISE, dissemination plays a central role in preparing the ground for exploitation and ensuring that the results of EO-based water intelligence solutions reach the intended user groups. It ensures that the value and applicability of results extend beyond the project consortium.

This document distinguishes dissemination (which shares project results with stakeholders who can best make use of them) from communication (which broadly promotes the project) and exploitation (which uses project results commercially or institutionally), while complementing and building upon previous deliverables including D2.1 Communication Strategy delivered at M3 (March 2025) and D2.5 Stakeholder Outreach Strategy delivered at M5 (May 2025). It provides detailed guidance on how to promote project outputs and how to prepare key stakeholders for using them. In doing so, it aims to stimulate not only visibility but also engagement, trust, and legacy-building.

The present document is composed of two sections:

1. **Dissemination of project results**, which outlines the objectives, the target audiences divided into three tier stakeholders' groups, the corresponding key messages and results to be disseminated to the different target audiences, the different types of dissemination activities, the tools and channels used and the timing of the dissemination activities. This section will also include the different roles and responsibilities of the project partners with regards to the dissemination of the project results, as well as the set dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in order to track the dissemination activities.
2. **Exploitation of project results**, which specifies the goals and means to reach them and provides an overview of the PCP WISE Key Exploitable Result (KER) and their potential end-users. It will include an investigation about the different types of exploitation: commercial, policy-oriented and scientific exploitation. The partners' responsibilities are described as well as the planning of the exploitation activities. Exploitation KPIs have been set in order to monitor the exploitation activities. Finally, an IPR strategy has been elaborated and reported in this section.

1. Dissemination of project results

Dissemination consists in sharing the research results with potential users or peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers. In order to disseminate the PCP WISE project results, a proper dissemination strategy has been established (Section 1.1), the different partners' role in the dissemination strategy were defined (Section 1.2) and KPIs were set in order to track the performance of our dissemination activities (Section 1.3).

1.1. PCP WISE Dissemination Strategy

Drawing on the PCP WISE Communication Strategy (D2.1), the PCP WISE Dissemination Strategy follows the 6W approach:

- Why: Which are the objectives of the dissemination strategy (Section 1.1.1)
- Whom: Who are the main stakeholders' group that will be targeted (Section 1.1.2)
- What: What are the key results, messages and information that will be disseminated (Section 1.1.3)
- Where: Through which channels will the key results be disseminated (Section 1.1.4)
- When: When will the key results be disseminated (Section 1.1.5)
- How: How will the key results be disseminated (Section 1.1.4)

1.1.1. Objectives

The PCP WISE's dissemination strategy is structured around four strategic objectives:

1. **Enhance visibility of the PCP (SO1):** Ensure that key audiences of PCP WISE are aware of the project's procurement process, its key dates and progress, innovations, and implications.
2. **Foster engagement (SO2):** Strengthen relationships with relevant stakeholders to support co-creation, knowledge sharing, and replication.
3. **Promote uptake and replication (SO3):** Enable public and private actors beyond the consortium to adopt PCP WISE solutions and approaches.
4. **Contribute to policy and practice (SO4):** Inform and influence innovation procurement practices and climate adaptation policies through evidence and experience from PCP WISE.

Each of these objectives will be supported by targeted activities, tools, and content over the lifecycle of the project. Dissemination is not a linear process but a continual dialogue with the ecosystem, leaving room to make adjustments and adaptations where needed.

1.1.2. Target audiences

Effective stakeholder outreach and engagement is central to PCP WISE’s success. Dissemination efforts are shaped by a comprehensive mapping of target audiences, aligned with stakeholder tiers identified both in the Grant Agreement and in D2.5 Stakeholder Outreach Strategy.

Figure 1 below helps capture and present the **characteristics, needs, and motivations** of key stakeholder groups in a clear and accessible format. It should be noted that the stakeholder terminology used in Figure 3 is outdated, reflecting the naming from the Grant Agreement. The current equivalents are as follows: Providers are now Suppliers, Buyers are Replicators, and Other Stakeholders are Followers as described in the sections hereafter.

Please refer to the legend below for clarification of the outreach approach found across stakeholder categories and tiers in Table 2:

Legend	
Tier 1 (Involved)	PCP WISE Buyers and contracted Suppliers.
Tier 2 (Engaged)	External buyers/ procurers (Replicators), suppliers not selected, funding organisations and investors (both public and private)
Tier 3 (Influencers)	Policymakers, funders, citizens, NGOs, and media.

Table 1: Stakeholder tiers' definition

Figure 1: PCP WISE Stakeholder Engagement Strategy. Source: Grant Agreement

At the start of the project, consortium partners coordinated across WPs to **harmonise the naming** of external stakeholder categories, as outlined below.

External Stakeholder Category	Description
Followers	Organisations and individuals interested in PCP WISE who are <u>not buyers or suppliers</u> – e.g., policymakers, networks, associations, EU projects, media, NGOs, and civil society – supporting advocacy and market uptake .
Replicators	<u>Public procurers/ buyers</u> outside the consortium interested in adopting PCP WISE solutions – e.g., municipalities, regions, ministries, water or environmental agencies, and authorities facing climate adaptation challenges – ensuring replicability of the project’s model and outcomes.
Suppliers	Also known as market “providers” or “contractors”, these are <u>companies, start-ups, and research organisations</u> developing EO-based solutions for PCP WISE buyers – e.g., EO tech providers, climate service providers, and water management innovators – that will respond to the September 202 call for tenders.

Table 2: External Stakeholder Glossary

At the time of this present deliverable (D2.2, June 2025), a total of 575 suppliers, 163 buyers (or replicators), and 173 EU projects or initiatives (or followers) have been added to the PCP WISE’s Stakeholder database and approached as part of targeted outreach efforts.

This segmentation allows PCP WISE to tailor messages and channels effectively, ensuring that dissemination activities meet diverse needs and produce high engagement.

1.1.3. Key messages to be disseminated

Based on the analysis of the interest and objectives of each stakeholder group, the key messages and results disseminated will be adapted to each of them. The following table summarises the key messages and results to be disseminated to the different stakeholder groups.

Stakeholder Category	Tier	Stakeholder sub-category	Messages and results to be disseminated
Suppliers	T1	Potential bidders to the call for tenders & Contractors selected for the PCP	- Dissemination of the Challenge brief and use cases’ description, tender documentation package (eligibility and award criteria), PCP calendar, tender package documentation, consortium requirements, and lessons from the OMC — to support high-quality, competitive, and well-informed bids.

Stakeholder Category	Tier	Stakeholder sub-category	Messages and results to be disseminated
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Updates on contract milestones, co-design expectations, visibility opportunities through project channels, and chances to influence EO-based water resilience innovations (Co-development framework, results of phase 1, 2 and 3, etc.)
	T2	Suppliers not selected for the PCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouragement to stay connected via Community Platform, future tendering and collaboration opportunities, updates on PCP results and supplier achievements (Summary of OMC insights, results of call for tenders, publishable summaries of PCP Phases etc.)
	T3	Innovation clusters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information on the PCP model as a business opportunity, project visibility for cluster members, and invitation to events and Community Platform to explore synergies.
Followers	T1	End-users (final beneficiaries of the solutions)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demonstration of solution relevance and benefits, user-centric value propositions, and opportunities to join testing or replication stages. - Pilot success stories showcasing impact on users.
	T2	Funding organisations (private & public)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence of demand-driven innovation, investment opportunities, alignment with green and digital EU agendas, and support for market entry of EO innovations. - Investment and scaling potential briefs
	T3	Policy & decision makers (at EU and national levels)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence-based insights on PCP as a strategic procurement tool, policy briefs linking PCP WISE to climate adaptation goals, and replicability potential. - Policy brief on lessons learned from the PCP process.

Stakeholder Category	Tier	Stakeholder sub-category	Messages and results to be disseminated
		Research organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge sharing from PCP-driven R&D, opportunities for collaboration and contribution to standardisation, and access to publicly available technical deliverables. - Synthesis of R&D methodologies and innovation outcomes.
		EU Networks & Projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Synergy building opportunities, cross-promotion of outcomes, and invitations to co-host events or thematic workshops. - Joint action briefs and cross-project learning insights.
		Environmental NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential impacts on climate resilience and water security, co-benefits of EO technologies, and opportunities to amplify public understanding. - Sustainability and societal impact summary.
		Media & opinion leaders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compelling stories on innovation and public value, access to visual and press materials, and spokesperson availability. - Press release and media-ready stories on project milestones.
Replicators	T1	End-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Practical benefits of EO-based solutions, testimonial use cases, and clear steps to replicate or adopt the solutions. - User adoption guides/ roadmap and tested prototypes.
	T2	Interested buyers/water agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to the PCP model, benefits of early engagement, success stories, and information on how to join the PCP WISE legacy. - Results from PCP pilots, capacity-building resources, policy alignment, and roadmap to prepare for replication or scaling up. - Replication roadmap and onboarding materials.

Table 3: PCP WISE Key messages and results to be disseminated

1.1.4. Dissemination tools and channels

PCP WISE employs a multi-channel approach, balancing digital presence, personal interaction, and high-quality documentation.

- **Direct contacts:** notably for the Tier 1 stakeholders, as they are directly involved in the case study activities they will be contacted and mobilised through direct contact (physical meetings, mailing, phone) by project partners. These will then be invited to follow and consult online dissemination channels to be informed about the project results.
- **Online dissemination:** through the PCP WISE website, Community Platform, newsletter, social media (LinkedIn), videos and online events.
- **Non-electronic dissemination:** through the project flyers, technical posters, banners, roll-ups, etc.
- **Physical interactive dissemination:** through participation at scientific and non-scientific events and the organisation of events.

Dissemination method	Dissemination channel	Resp. Partner	Results/ Outcomes disseminated
Online dissemination	Website	GAC with the input from all partners	Project overview, call for tenders, PCP calendar, challenge brief, news updates, key deliverables, and results from pilots and policy briefs.
	Community platform	Enrich Global (EG) with contribution of all partners for news creation	Supplier engagement resources, matchmaking tools, OMC outcomes, tender documentation, and interaction space for followers, replicators, and suppliers.
	Social media (LinkedIn, Youtube)	GAC	Highlights of events (e.g. OMC, Info Days), success stories, interviews, video explainers on the PCP process, solution spotlights, and consortium activities.
	Newsletters	GAC with input from all partners	Periodic updates on project progress, upcoming tenders or events, key lessons from PCP phases, and links to new resources on the website.
	Online events	GAC, Corvers, HwH, with the input from all partners	Live dissemination of tender calls, procurement guidance, stakeholder feedback sessions, and interim/pilot results presentations.
Non-electronic dissemination	Flyers	GAC	Concise overview of the project, PCP model explanation, timeline, and contact points for interested stakeholders.

Dissemination method	Dissemination channel	Resp. Partner	Results/ Outcomes disseminated
	Posters	GAC, HwH	Visual presentation of project objectives, EO-based challenges, PCP structure, and replicator engagement opportunities.
	Roll-ups	GAC	Key messages and branding displayed at conferences and events to raise visibility and attract interest.
	Social media banners	GAC	Promotional graphics for events, milestones (e.g. call opening), and campaigns aimed at increasing awareness and traffic to digital platforms.
Physical dissemination	Events	GAC & all partners, especially WP Leaders and all Buyers	Targeted sharing of challenge briefs, PCP methodology, pilot solution outcomes, and replicability guidance; engagement with replicators and followers.
	Final event	GAC and Lead Buyer	Comprehensive presentation of PCP WISE outcomes, co-developed solutions, policy and procurement lessons learned, and post-project legacy actions.

Table 4. PCP WISE Dissemination channels

1.1.5. Timeline of dissemination activities

PCP WISE dissemination channels and tools were developed to support the various phases of the PCP process:

- Preparatory Phase (M1 January 2025 –M8 August 2025): Awareness building, supplier engagement, Info Days, Open Market Consultations (OMCs), Call for tenders' visibility, stakeholder activation.
- Tender Phase (M8 August 2025 – M13 January 2026): Use case and bid preparation clarifications towards suppliers, suppliers' matchmaking support.
- Post-Tender (M14 February 2026 – M30 June 2027): Results dissemination, capacity building, replicator outreach.
- Final Phase (M31 July 2027 – M36 December 2027): Final event, exploitation launch, legacy materials.

Each phase has specific activities, outputs, and channels suited to the evolving needs of the target audience.

Dissemination channels and tools	Timing
Website	Established at M3 (March 2025) and continuously updated along the project duration

Dissemination channels and tools	Timing
Community Platform	Established at M1 (January 2025) and continuously updated along the project duration
Newsletter	Every 6 months
Flyers	Developed at M1 (January 2025)
Posters	
Online Banners	All along the project duration
Roll-ups	Developed at M1 (January 2025)
Press release	Developed at M5 (May 2025)
Online & physical events	All along the project duration
6 videos	First at M6 (June 2025) and all along the project duration
One policy brief	At M34 (October 2027)
White papers – stakeholder engagement	At M35 (November 2027)
Two white papers - exploitation	At M36 (December 2027)

Table 5: Timeline of PCP WISE dissemination tools and channels' preparation

1.2. Partner-specific roles in dissemination

GAC is responsible for the dissemination task with ENRICH GLOBAL as an affiliated entity of GAC, and the support of WP2 Task leaders, namely Aerospace Valley and Evenflow. Nevertheless, all PCP WISE partners are directly involved in dissemination tasks maximising opportunities related to their profile, action field and geographical location, which will help grow the impact of the results' dissemination.

GAC, together with Corvers Procurement Services is responsible for establishing the dissemination and exploitation strategy for the project results. This dissemination strategy will be presented and discussed during a set consortium meeting in order to plan the dissemination of the project's results, lessons learnt and feedback.

Moreover, in order to gather information about the partners' dissemination activities, GAC has established an Excel tracking document. This Excel sheet has been shared with all partners on the project's sharing platform (Microsoft Teams), which are responsible for reporting their dissemination activities on an ongoing basis.

All project partners are involved in this task and more specifically in the participation in online and physical events with the aim to disseminate the project opportunities and results during events as well as in online dissemination with the aim to disseminate the project results produced via their own network.

1.3. Dissemination KPI

In order to track the dissemination activities several indicators and KPIs have been established. These are consulted and reported regularly during the WP2 meetings in order to monitor the progress of the activities and to readjust the consortium's efforts if needed.

The following table summarises the established dissemination activities indicators.

#	Indicator	Target	WP
1	Number of stakeholders consulted throughout the project	200+	2
2	Number of website visitors (by the end of 3rd year)	4000+	2
3	Number of news posted on the Website per year	20	2
4	Number of followers on social media Platforms (LinkedIn, YouTube)	300+	2
5	Number of posts on LinkedIn per year	40	2
6	Number of events organised online or physical events (etc.)	25+	2
7	Number of newsletters	5	2
8	Number of newsletters subscribers (or users of platform, or subscriber)	100+	2
9	Number of events in which the project partners participate in/ attend	30+	2
10	Number of digital flyers/ infographics	6+	2
11	Number of videos (1 promotional, 1 for each of the use cases and 1 final video)	8	2
12	Number of roll-ups	2	2
13	Number of experts/ stakeholders in the PCP-WISE Community platform	60	2
14	White papers	2	2
15	Number of providers identified	100+	3, 2
16	Stakeholder Workshops	3	5
17	User Interactions & Interviews	10	5
18	Targeted guidance documents	10	5
19	Learning Materials	8	5
20	Solution provided by the market as input to phase 1	40	3
21	Quality of solutions provided on top of mandatory SWVA solution	>50%	4
22	Number of investors reached	>20	2

Table 6: PCP WISE KPI table

2. Exploitation of Results

PCP WISE aims to deliver tangible, scalable innovations that enhance climate resilience through EO-based water intelligence solutions. The exploitation strategy ensures that the project's results are not only disseminated but also used, scaled, and sustained beyond the end of the project — whether commercially, institutionally, or in policy frameworks. This section outlines the strategy, pathways, responsibilities, planning activities, and indicators to monitor the successful exploitation of PCP WISE outcomes.

2.1. PCP WISE exploitation strategy

The exploitation strategy presented in this section is a **tentative proposal** that outlines the preliminary framework, roles, and activities planned to maximise the uptake and sustainability of PCP WISE results. It reflects the project's early insights and strategic direction but is **not final**. This draft will be **further refined, validated, and enriched** through partner collaboration, stakeholder feedback, and evolving project outcomes. A more detailed and operational exploitation plan will be developed and delivered as a separate report at **M17 (May 2026)** of the project, aligning with the completion of Phase 1 of the PCP process (Preparation phase).

2.1.1. Commercial and policy-oriented exploitation strategy

The PCP WISE exploitation strategy targets two main pathways:

- **Commercial exploitation** both by the Public Buyers Goup (PBG) and suppliers, enabling them to bring co-developed solutions to the broader EU market after the PCP process, mainly through an intellectual property regime that provides use rights (licenses) to the buyers and leaves the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) vested in the suppliers, together with the obligation to protect and exploit the results of the PCP.
- **Policy and institutional exploitation** by public buyers and replicators, supporting the integration of innovative procurement and climate intelligence tools into operational practices and policy agendas.

Key elements of this strategy include:

- A **Replication Roadmap** aimed at external buyers and water authorities.
- A **Legacy Package** including post-project guidelines, licensing options, and onboarding materials.
- **Matchmaking and investment-oriented activities** to support PBG and suppliers' commercial scale-up.

2.1.2. Scientific exploitation and knowledge transfer

PCP WISE will contribute to scientific progress by:

- Engaging with academic and R&D communities via conferences and working groups.

- Contributing to the standardisation of EO-based climate services and water monitoring tools.

2.1.3. Partners' role and responsibilities

Exploitation is a cross-cutting effort led by:

- **GAC** and **CORVERS**, co-leading the overall exploitation strategy, including legal and commercial pathways.
- **Buyers' group members**, who serve as early adopters and reference users for replicability.
- **Suppliers**, who are responsible for commercial planning and alignment of solution development with market needs.
- **Evenflow and Aerospace Valley**, supporting outreach to innovation ecosystems and clusters.
- **All partners**, contributing by engaging their networks, participating in events, and co-developing exploitation materials.

2.1.4. Planning of exploitation activities

Exploitation will follow a phased approach:

- **M1, January 2025 – M17, May 2026 (Preparation)**: Identify Key Exploitable Results (KERs), set legal framework, begin supplier engagement and supporters engagement like investors and Venture Capitals.
- **M17, May 2026 – M27, March 2027 (During PCP Phases 1 solution design & Phase 2 prototype development)**: Capture emerging results, initiate replicator dialogue, develop support tools.
- **M27, March 2027 – M36, December 2027 (During PCP Phase 3 & Final Phase)**:
 - Pilot showcasing, impact assessment, stakeholder co-design of legacy outputs.
 - Launch of Replication Roadmap, final event, white papers on policy and commercial opportunities, finalisation of post-project exploitation actions.

Key tools will include:

- Investment briefs for funders and investors.
- Policy briefs for regional/national decision-makers.
- Use case testimonials and adoption guides for replicators.

2.2. IPR Strategy

2.2.1. Purpose and principles

The Intellectual Property Right (IPR) strategy of PCP WISE aims to foster innovation while safeguarding the rights of suppliers and ensuring that public buyers retain sufficient access to (and use of) results for validation, policy input, and potential scaling. It is grounded in the Horizon Europe PCP model and reflects a balanced risk-benefit sharing under market conditions, in line with the provisions of the Model Grant Agreement and Annex H.

This IPR approach:

- Ensures that **ownership of R&D results (foreground IPR)** remains with suppliers, supporting their ability to commercialise innovative solutions.
- Grants (indefinite) **usage rights to buyers** for internal use, testing, and replication planning.
- Encourages **transparency and compliance** throughout the procurement process, including proper management of background and foreground IPRs.
- Supports the **reuse, adaptation, and uptake** of PCP WISE solutions by external buyers and market stakeholders beyond the consortium.

2.2.2. IPR allocation and legal framework

Following the Horizon Europe guidelines, PCP WISE implements the following principles for IPR allocation:

- **Suppliers retain IPR ownership** of the foreground results developed during the PCP phases.
- **Buyers retain a royalty-free, non-exclusive license** to use non-commercially the results for their internal needs and for the purpose of testing and further procurement preparation.
- **Further commercial exploitation** by suppliers is encouraged and supported, including through legacy packages, investment briefs, and matchmaking activities.
- The **tender documents and framework agreements** include detailed clauses on the IPR distribution and specific arrangements, in particular on background IPR declarations, data access, confidentiality, and licensing conditions.
- **Joint ownership**, where applicable, will be negotiated based on contributions and co-development efforts during prototype design or piloting.

2.2.3. IPR management across PCP phases

Each phase of the PCP WISE process embeds IPR provisions:

- **Phase 1 (Solution Design)**: Contractors declare relevant background IPR; contracts include confidentiality terms and clarity on expected outputs.
- **Phase 2 (Prototype Development)**: Contractors declare relevant background IPR; (PCP phase) contracts include confidentiality terms and clarity on expected outputs (also based on end of phase 1 feedback); new generated IP are indicated (if applicable); rights and usage of prototypes are defined, including any co-created methodologies, indicators, or dashboards.
- **Phase 3 (Pilot Testing)**: Contractors declare relevant background IPR; (PCP phase) contracts include confidentiality terms and clarity on expected outputs (also based on end of phase 2 feedback); new generated IP are indicated (if applicable); end-users validate solutions in operational environments; final IPR reports are collected to confirm rights allocation and usage boundaries.

The Framework Agreement also includes relevant provisions that will be applicable during the whole duration of the PCP. Those provisions will ensure that the suppliers retain the ownership of results of the PCP and protect them. Failure to protect these results or to further commercialise the technology enables the Public Buyers Group to activate a call back clause; i.e., the possibility to claim the ownership of the IPR. Additionally, the possibility to request

the suppliers to grant royalty-free, non-exclusive licenses under FRAND (Fair, Reasonable, and Non-Discrimination) conditions to selected third parties is envisaged.

2.2.4. Risk mitigation measures

To ensure legal certainty and prevent disputes, PCP WISE implements the following safeguards:

- All contractors are required to sign **IPR declarations** and submit detailed foreground/background IPR descriptions.
- A dedicated **legal advisory function** (led by Corvers) supports the Lead Procurer and Buyers Group on contract structuring and IPR compliance.
- IPR issues will be addressed as part of the **OMC**, helping to build trust between buyers and potential suppliers.
- Dispute resolution mechanisms are embedded in Framework Agreements.

2.2.5. Post-project use and licensing

To enable wider uptake and market impact after the PCP:

- Suppliers will be encouraged to **license validated solutions** to other public buyers under FRAND (Fair, Reasonable and Non-Discriminatory) and transparent conditions.
- Buyers and replicators will be provided with **onboarding and replication packages** that respect suppliers' IPR while enabling further use.
- Non-commercial outputs (e.g., use case templates, policy briefs, taxonomies) may be published under open access or Creative Commons licenses, subject to approval.

2.2.6. Oversight and responsibilities

- **Corvers and the PBG lead** the definition and monitoring of the legal framework for IPR and procurement documentation.
- **Corvers and the PBG** ensure strategic alignment of IPR handling with exploitation goals.
- **Suppliers** are responsible for documenting and reporting any background IPR and agreeing to PCP-specific IPR terms and post-contract exploitation obligations.
- **All partners** contribute to monitoring, awareness-raising, and proper use of IPR-related outputs within and beyond the consortium.

3. Conclusion & Next Steps

The dissemination plan presented in this deliverable provides a roadmap for amplifying the results and reach of PCP WISE. By activating multiple channels, adapting to different audiences, and closely aligning with stakeholder needs, the plan supports the long-term vision of replicable, EO-based climate services for water resilience.

Next steps include aligning dissemination activities with the First Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (D2.9) and using this plan to coordinate partner activities and track impact through KPIs and stakeholder feedback.